

Enhanced spin relaxation time in a 2D/1D van der Waals hybrid heterostructure

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The key attraction of graphene in spintronics arises from its high electronic mobility and low intrinsic spin-orbit coupling (SOC), which enable long spin relaxation times. However, the weak SOC limits the ability to control spin currents within graphene. A promising strategy for enhancing the spin functionalities of graphene is to introduce proximity effects with other materials. In this context, molecular compounds show great potential for tuning the spin properties of graphene. Here, we present a novel fabrication methodology that integrates molecular compounds with graphene-based spintronic nanodevices using stencil hBN masks, allowing us to investigate the resulting spin-related effects. First, our non-destructive fabrication technique, confirmed by micro-Raman spectroscopy, preserves the integrity of the molecular compound. Moreover, by combining experimental Hanle precession with a 3D spin diffusion model, we demonstrate that Fullerene C₆₀ molecules enhance the spin relaxation time of the graphene. The established fabrication methodology can be further expanded to integrate graphene with exotic molecular compounds, such as photochromic and spin cross-over molecules, enabling the exploration of proximity-induced spin phenomena and paving the way for spin-based multifunctional nanodevices.

1. Introduction

Graphene and other two-dimensional (2D) van der Waals materials^[1,2] exhibit unique properties, such as tunable band gaps, exceptional mechanical strength and high surface-to-volume ratio, making them ideal candidates for advanced electronic applications. The potential of graphene and 2D materials can be further enhanced by incorporating them into hybrid heterostructures that combine 2D materials with other materials, such as organic molecules, which would add extra functionalities to the electronic device. Indeed, hybrid heterostructures composed of 2D materials and organic molecules have been extensively employed to tune the electronic and opto-electronic properties of graphene and other related 2D materials.^[3-9]

Like electronic devices, graphene has emerged as a prime material for spintronics due to its exceptional properties. Of special interest is the high electronic mobility of graphene^[10,11] which allows the fast transport of spin polarized current and the weak intrinsic spin-orbit coupling (SOC) which enables long spin relaxation time.^[12,15] However, the weak SOC of graphene creates difficulties for the manipulation of spins and limits graphene contribution to versatile spintronic devices. To develop advanced graphene-based spintronic devices, it is essential to tune and control the spin functionalities of the device. One approach is the proximity effect in which graphene is interfaced with other 2D van der Waals materials,^[16-21] with heavy and light metal oxide^[22,23] and with surface adatoms.^[24-27]

An underexplored class of materials in graphene-based spintronic devices is organic molecules. Integrating organic molecular compounds with spintronic devices offers a plethora of opportunities to fine tune the device spin functionalities. Previous attempts to explore the effects of molecules on graphene spin valves typically involved depositing molecules across the entire device.^[28] This approach intertwines the molecular influence on spin

transport with unintended side effects, such as changes to charge injection at the electrodes and direct interactions with the magnetic components. Therefore, it is crucial to selectively interface only the desired spin transport channel with the molecular layer while preserving the integrity of the surrounding device. However, achieving this high level of spatial precision is challenging, as organic molecules are highly sensitive to conventional nanofabrication techniques and, therefore, advanced fabrication methods are required.

In this paper, we demonstrate a unique spintronic device architecture in which the chemical functionalization of graphene with fullerene (C_{60}) molecules enables devices with enhanced spin relaxation times. Our device architecture is based on a novel fabrication methodology which involves the pick-up and drop^[29-31] of custom-etched hexagonal boron nitride (hBN) masks onto graphene spintronic nanodevices. This fabrication strategy enables the seamless integration of hybrid organic-inorganic interfaces into spintronic devices, allowing for the combination of molecules with distinctive functionalities, such as photochromic^[32-34] and spin crossover molecules,^[35-37] with 2D spintronic devices. Our approach lays the foundation for the development of hybrid, multifunctional spintronic nanodevices.

2. Results and discussion

Figure 1 shows a comprehensive sketch of the developed fabrication methodology. First, we mechanically exfoliate hBN flakes onto a doped silicon substrate with 300 nm of silicon oxide - Si/SiO₂ (300 nm), in ambient conditions using scotch tape. The desired flake is then identified under an optical microscope. Next, we nanopattern a window slit onto the hBN flake using electron-beam lithography followed by the reactive-ion etching with SF₆/Ar. The etched hBN is kept in room temperature acetone for 12 hours to clean the residual electron-beam resist (poly(methyl methacrylate) - PMMA). The result is a custom-etched hBN mask with a slit as observed in Figure 1. In this case, the slit is 0.5 μm wide and 10 μm long. The Si/SiO₂ substrate which contains the hBN mask is then stored in an Ar-filled glovebox for later use.

At a second stage, we exfoliate graphene flakes onto a different Si/SiO₂ (300 nm) substrate in a cleanroom environment using scotch tape and identify the required flake under an optical microscope. After exfoliation, we fabricate a graphene lateral spin valve (LSV) by combining graphene with ferromagnetic TiO_x/Co electrodes, using standard nanofabrication techniques. Details of the fabrication are given in the supporting information. After fabrication, the substrate with the LSV device is immediately transferred into an Ar-filled glovebox to prevent air-oxidation of the ferromagnetic electrodes.

Third, the hBN mask which is on a sacrificial substrate is transferred onto the graphene LSV device and the slit is precisely placed in-between two consecutive ferromagnetic electrodes separated by 2.7 μm. The transfer is done via dry pick-up and drop technique using LCC (Lakme color crush) polymer^[29-31] details of which are described in the supporting information. The obtained graphene LSV device with the hBN mask is dipped in a 1:3

mixture of acetone/isopropanol for 8 hours to clean the residues of the pick-up polymer.

Figure 1. Workflow of the fabrication methodology. Steps: (0) Exfoliation of a hBN flake onto a Si/SiO₂ (300 nm) substrate. (1) Creation of hBN mask via reactive ion etching (RIE) of a slit. The width of the slit is 0.5 µm and the length is 10 µm. (2) Pick-up of the hBN mask with transparent convex LCC polymer (orange circular spot) deposited onto PDMS gel-film (dark grey small square) which is anchored onto the pick-up slide glass (light grey big rectangle). (3) Transfer of the hBN mask on the fabricated graphene LSV device, having ferromagnetic electrodes. The distance between two consecutive ferromagnetic electrodes is 2.7 µm. (4) Final LSV device after stamping the hBN mask and deposition of C₆₀ (5nm) molecules. The hBN mask is aligned precisely in between two consecutive ferromagnetic electrodes. The inset shows a sketch of the crystal structure of the region in which C₆₀ (brown buckyballs) is proximitized to the graphene (grey carbon sheet).

Finally, the device is introduced into an ultra-high vacuum evaporation chamber to deposit organic molecules. 5 nm of C₆₀ molecular film is deposited onto the device, where the molecules penetrate through the slit, adsorb on the graphene surface and create graphene/organic molecule hybrid structure. The optical image of the final device is depicted in Figure 1 and the sketch of the proximitized graphene/C₆₀ structure is shown in the inset. This fabrication methodology enables graphene LSV devices which simultaneously contain pristine and proximitized (with C₆₀) graphene while preserving the integrity of the organic molecular compound.

In addition to acting as a mask slit, the hBN flake brings different advantages. Firstly, the hBN mask will encapsulate the remaining graphene channel and protect graphene's surface from surrounding contamination consequently preserving its intrinsic electronic properties. Secondly, the hBN mask will also protect the ferromagnetic electrodes from atmospheric contamination. This is crucial for the functionality of LSV devices, since the ferromagnetic electrodes are the spin injector/detector and maintaining the pristine magnetic anisotropy and the health of the ferromagnetic electrodes is of great importance.

To investigate whether the developed fabrication methodology is non-destructive to both graphene and C₆₀, we characterized the structural, charge transport, and spin transport properties of both pristine and proximitized graphene using transport measurements micro-Raman spectroscopy.

The bottom panel of **Figure 2** compares the Raman spectrum of SiO₂/C₆₀ (5 nm) reference region with the one of SiO₂/graphene/C₆₀ (5 nm) proximitized region (after adsorption of C₆₀ onto graphene through the hBN slit). The spectra of both regions show the typical vibrational modes of C₆₀. Specifically, the peaks at 1425 cm⁻¹ and 1462 cm⁻¹ which represent the dominant H_g (7) and A_g (2) modes of C₆₀^[38] are clearly observed in the

SiO₂/graphene/C₆₀ proximitized region. Moreover, the H_g (8) mode of C₆₀ at higher frequencies 1570 cm⁻¹ appears as a shoulder-like peak in the G-peak of the graphene and is clearly observed in the fitting of the G-peak with two Lorentzian functions. The presence of these features in both the reference C₆₀ and the proximitized graphene/C₆₀ regions confirms that C₆₀ molecules travel through the hBN mask slit and create a homogeneous molecular film on the graphene.

The full-range spectrum of the graphene channel (top panel of Figure 2) exhibits the clear G and 2D characteristic peaks of graphene.^[39] The zoomed-in spectrum of the 2D peak is well fitted using a single Lorentzian function confirming that the graphene is monolayer (Figure S1, supporting information). After confirming the structural characteristics of the graphene and the integrity of C₆₀ in the proximitized region, we studied the charge transport properties.

Figure 2. Structural properties. Top panel: Full-range Raman spectrum of the monolayer graphene. Middle panel: SiO₂/C₆₀ reference spectrum. The black scattered symbols represent the experimental spectrum, and the blue solid line is the fitted result. Bottom panel: Raman spectrum of the graphene/C₆₀ proximitized region, and its inset is a sketch of the proximitized structure. Red scattered symbols are the experimental spectrum, and the olive solid line is the fitted result. The Raman peaks at 1425 cm⁻¹ and 1462 cm⁻¹ are clear and similar in both regions. The peak at 1570 cm⁻¹ appears as a shoulder-like peak after fitting the G peak of the graphene with two Lorentzian functions.

The schematic of the LSV device with the charge transport measurement configuration is shown in **Figure 3a**.

Figure 3. Charge transport properties. a) Schematics of the device with the electrical configuration for charge transport measurements. The black and magenta circuit diagrams represent the measurement configuration for the pristine region and the hybrid region (the channel which consists of one-part pristine graphene and one-part graphene/ C_{60}), respectively. The yellow region corresponds to C_{60} (5 nm) deposited through the slit. F1 to F5 are the ferromagnetic electrodes. b) Four-probe resistance of the pristine channel (black plot) and the hybrid channel (magenta plot) as a function of back-gate voltage (V_{bg}) and carrier concentration (n), recorded at $T = 100\text{K}$.

The resistance of the hybrid graphene channel (which consists of both pristine graphene and proximitized graphene/ C_{60}) and the pristine graphene channel as a function of back-gate voltage (V_{bg}) is measured with a four-probe configuration. A constant charge current (I_C) of $10\ \mu\text{A}$ is applied between F1 and F2 electrodes, and the voltage drop is recorded between electrodes F4 and F5 for the pristine graphene (V_{Gr}), and between electrodes F3 and F4 for the hybrid graphene ($V_{Hybrid\ Gr}$). Figure 3b represents the transfer curves of the pristine graphene (black plot) and the hybrid graphene (magenta plot) measured at $T = 100\text{K}$. The resistance of both regions reveals a representative Dirac feature with a maximum corresponding to the charge neutrality point (CNP). The CNP for both

pristine and hybrid graphene sits at -0.5 V which implies that graphene maintains its carrier concentration over the entire channel.

The field-effect mobility (μ_{FE}) of the graphene channel is calculated directly from the V_{bg} dependence of the conductivity (σ):

$$\mu_{FE} = \frac{d\sigma}{dV_{bg}} \times \frac{1}{C_{bg}}, \quad (1)$$

where C_{bg} is the back-gate capacitance.

In the low doping regime, the mobility of pristine graphene is $\mu_{FE(Gr)} = 41000 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ while the mobility of the hybrid graphene is $\mu_{FE(Hybrid Gr)} = 22000 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. It is worth mentioning that the extracted carrier mobility of the pristine graphene channel is higher compared to the mobilities of graphene in graphene/transition metal dichalcogenide spin valve devices.^[40,41] This high carrier mobility reflects on the superior quality of our devices, fabricated following the novel methodology explained above. However, it is important to note that the calculated mobility of the hybrid graphene $\mu_{FE(Hybrid Gr)}$ is not the mobility of the graphene in contact with only C₆₀ rather it represents the effective mobility of the entire channel in the hybrid region consisting of one-part proximitized graphene/C₆₀ and two-parts of pristine graphene/hBN areas. To find the mobility of the proximitized graphene/C₆₀ region only, we first calculated its resistance from the total measured resistance of the hybrid region, details of which are described in the supporting information. Consequently, this resistance is converted to conductivity and the mobility of the proximitized graphene/C₆₀ region is extracted following Equation (1). The mobility of the proximitized graphene/C₆₀ region is $\approx 10000 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and shows four-fold and two-fold decrease compared to the mobility of pristine graphene and of hybrid region, respectively (Figure S3, supporting information). This shows that, in the proximitized region, C₆₀ molecules act as extrinsic impurities for charge carriers. C₆₀ molecules are charge neutral compounds, and in the hybrid channel, the molecules remain neutral since there is no charge

transfer between the graphene and the molecules as observed from the transfer curves of Figure 3b. Moreover, C₆₀ molecules have negligible effective SOC strength compared to light and heavy transition metals, hence ruling out charged and SOC induced impurities as causes of the decrease in mobility. Therefore, C₆₀ molecules act as point-like impurity defects in the hybrid region. These C₆₀ molecules hinder the free motion of charge carriers and subsequently decrease the charge carrier mobility.

Next, to study the spin transport properties, we conducted non-local Hanle precession measurements in the pristine and the hybrid graphene channels. In this case, a magnetic field is applied along the out-of-plane axis of Co i.e. along the z – direction (B_z), where the spins experience Larmor precession in the $x - y$ plane while diffusing along the x – direction of the graphene channel. Consequently, the Hanle curves are acquired by recording the non-local resistance (R_{nl}) of the device (see black and magenta circuits in **Figure 4a** for each channel under study) as a function B_z after setting the ferromagnetic injector and detector electrodes in a parallel (R_{nl}^P) or antiparallel (R_{nl}^{AP}) magnetic configuration. Typically, the net spin precession signal $\Delta R_{nl} = (R_{nl}^P - R_{nl}^{AP})/2$ is then fitted with an analytical 1D spin diffusion model to extract the spin diffusion constant (D_s) and the spin lifetime (τ_s) of graphene. The spin diffusion length (λ_s) is calculated as $\lambda_s = \sqrt{D_s \tau_s}$.

Whereas the Hanle curves shown in Figure 4b and 4c correspond to the pristine graphene channel for $n = 0.6 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, the Hanle curves in Figure 4d and 4e correspond to the entire hybrid channel measured for the same n (for a comprehensive study, the Hanle precession measurements are repeated for a wide range of n). Fitting those curves with the simple analytical 1D spin diffusion model would misestimate the spin transport parameters of the proximitized graphene/C₆₀ region, which is the region of most interest. Hence, we employ a 3D Finite Element Method (FEM) with the spin diffusion model to capture the spatial distribution of the charge and

spin currents in the different regions of the device and, consequently, accurately extract the spin transport properties of the proximitized graphene/C₆₀ region.

Figure 4. Spin transport properties. a) Schematics of the non-local Hanle precession measurements. The black and magenta circuit diagrams represent the measurement configuration for the pristine and the hybrid graphene, respectively. b) Hanle precession measurement, corresponding to R_{nl} as a function of out-of-plane magnetic field (B_z) with F4 and F5 electrodes set in parallel (R_{nl}^P , blue line) and antiparallel (R_{nl}^{AP} , red line) magnetic configuration for pristine graphene. c) Net Hanle precession signal extracted from the two curves in (b) with $\Delta R_{nl} = (R_{nl}^P - R_{nl}^{AP})/2$. d,e) Same as panels (b) and (c), for hybrid graphene. Green scattered points are the experimental data, and black solid lines (with circles) are the fits using the 3D FEM model. All measurements are recorded at $T = 100\text{K}$ and for $n = 0.6 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$.

The simulation is carried out by first defining the geometry of the system (**Figure 5a**) through SEM images (**Figure S6**, supporting information). Next, the fitting of the Hanle precession curves depends on three main parameters: D_s , τ_s , and graphene/ferromagnetic electrode interface polarization (P_i). Ideally, we would perform a simultaneous fitting by varying all three parameters. However, in practice, this approach is computationally expensive. To simplify the task, we note that while D_s and τ_s affect both the shape line and the magnitude of the Hanle precession signal, P_i affects only the magnitude. Since, in this study, we are primarily interested in the relative values of the spin transport properties for the different regions of the graphene, we do not consider the value of P_i . Therefore, we normalize the simulation by fixing the point at $B_z = 0$ to the same resistance value as the experimental Hanle data and then fit the normalized experimental data using only D_s and τ_s .

For the graphene, we have two distinct regions shown in Figure 5a. The parameters we need are the resistivity, D_s , and τ_s . The resistivity of the pristine graphene is calculated using four-probe measurements while the resistivity of proximitized graphene/C₆₀ is calculated using a series resistance model. The equations solved for the system is the spin diffusion equation shown in Equation 2, which is solved separately for each region of the device and for each spin potential i.e. polarized along $\pm x, \pm y$ and $\pm z$.

$$\frac{D_s}{\rho} \frac{\partial^2 \mu}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\mu}{\rho \tau_s} + \frac{\omega \times \mu}{\rho} = 0, \quad (2)$$

where μ can be the chemical potential of spin-up or spin-down electrons in each of the cardinal directions, respectively. The first term of Equation 2 corresponds to the diffusion of the spin accumulation, the second term corresponds to the spin relaxation, and the third term, $\omega \times \mu$, where $\omega = \frac{g \mu_B B_z}{\hbar}$ is the Larmor frequency, with g being the Landé g-factor, μ_B the Bohr

magnetron, and \hbar is the reduced Planck's constant, represents the spin precession due to an external or effective magnetic field.

Next, the charge or spin currents are computed by taking the gradient of the total charge/spin potentials respectively. Figure 5b shows the charge chemical potential, which is the sum of all the individual potentials and its gradient gives the charge current density (Figure 5c). This follows the path of the applied current, noting that only the component in graphene is displayed for clarity. Whereas Figure 5d and 5e show the spin potential and the spin current decaying exponentially away from the injecting electrode under zero magnetic field, Figure 5f represents the spin potential under magnetic field of 0.3T.

We first studied the spin diffusion in the pristine channel. The experimental Hanle precession for this channel is available (Figure 4c) so to simulate the data we run the 3D FEM simulation for several values of the experimental magnetic field. This is repeated for an array of D_s and τ_s till we achieve a least square difference between simulation and experiment. Here we extract the spin diffusion parameters in the pristine graphene: $D_{s(pristine)}$, $\tau_{s(pristine)}$ and $\lambda_{s(pristine)}$. Next, the hybrid channel consists of two distinct regions: pristine graphene and proximitized graphene/C₆₀. The pristine parts of this hybrid channel are assumed to have the same diffusion properties as the pristine graphene channel. We therefore put the previously computed values of those parameters into the pristine parts of this hybrid channel. The values of $D_{s(proxy)}$ and $\tau_{s(proxy)}$ in the proximitized graphene/C₆₀ are found by simulating the experimental Hanle curves of the hybrid region (Figure 4e) over an array of $D_{s(proxy)}$ and $\tau_{s(proxy)}$ values until a minimum error compared to the experimental values is achieved.

The spin diffusion parameters of the pristine and the proximitized graphene/C₆₀ regions as a function of n are shown in Figure 5g-5i. In Figure 5g, the spin diffusion constant D_s ($prox$) in the proximitized region shows a drastic drop compared to the D_s ($pristine$) of pristine graphene. This means that spin polarized carriers in the proximitized region diffuse slower, spatially and in time, than in the pristine graphene. This is consistent with the reduction in the charge carrier mobility of the proximitized graphene/C₆₀ region discussed above and presented in Figure S3. Moreover, we observe an increase of the spin relaxation time τ_s ($prox$) in the presence of C₆₀ molecules (Figure 5h). Finally, the spin diffusion length in the proximitized region (λ_s ($prox$) = $\sqrt{D_s$ ($prox$) τ_s ($prox$)}) is shorter compared to the λ_s ($pristine$) of the pristine graphene, for the entire range of n under study, as seen in Figure 5i.

Figure 5. a) Geometry of the system showing pristine graphene (blue), proximitized graphene (green), as well as the charge current and voltage probes. b) Charge potential in the system. c) Gradient of the charge potential, showing charge current density. d) Spin potential, under no applied field, decaying exponentially away from the injecting electrode. e) The spin current, computed by taking the gradient of (d). f) Spin potential with polarization, with vector direction showing polarization, and magnitude showing the potential (under magnetic field of 0.3T). g) Spin diffusion constant, h) Spin lifetime i) Spin diffusion length as a function of n . Black plots are for pristine graphene and olive plots are for graphene/C₆₀. All measurements are recorded at $T = 100\text{K}$.

An enhancement of spin relaxation time with a proportional decrease in spin diffusion constant may be understood through an enhanced g factor due to localized magnetic moments and the exchange-field model.^[42,43] In this model, the exchange field created by the magnetic moments will display anomalies in the measured spin valve signal e.g. a dip and peak should appear in the spin signal with sweeping the B_y magnetic field. However, as seen in the spin valve signal in the plot of Figure S4b, there is no dip nor peak present for the full range of the magnetic field. Furthermore, C₆₀ molecules are non-magnetic compounds with zero magnetic moments and cannot accept spins from the graphene because of its high resistance. Therefore, these explanations do not comply with our graphene/C₆₀ system.

It must be noted that a previous work of self-assembled molecules on graphene^[28] showed a decrease in spin relaxation time with the reduction of spin diffusion constant since the self-assembled molecules create additional spin-flip scattering sites. This is not the case for our device since the spin relaxation processes are diminished by the presence of the C₆₀ molecules and now the spins experience fewer spin-flip sites in the graphene channel. The increase in spin relaxation time, coupled with the

decrease in the spin diffusion constant, in the graphene/C₆₀ proximitized region, promotes a dominant spin relaxation mechanism of the Dyakonov-Perel^[44,45] model compared to that of Elliot-Yafet mechanism,^[46,47] in which the electron spin flips its polarization due to scattering with defects, such as impurities and phonons, of high SOC. This is consistent with the fact that C₆₀ molecules are composed of only carbon atoms with negligible effective SOC, and hence a SOC induced spin relaxation mechanisms (Elliot-Yafet model) are negligible.

3. Conclusion

Using a new spintronic nanodevice architecture we have shown that C₆₀ molecules behave as extrinsic impurity defects on graphene, leading to the reduction of the graphene's carrier mobility and the spin diffusion constant. Despite this reduction, we have demonstrated - with an in-depth combination of experimental Hanle precession and 3D FEM simulation, that C₆₀ molecules in proximity to graphene increase the spin relaxation time and thus reduce the spin relaxation mechanisms. The increase in spin relaxation time alongside the decrease in spin diffusion constant indicates that the dominant spin relaxation mechanism is of the Dyakonov-Perel.

Our findings offer a novel approach for fabrication of nanoscale spintronic devices based on hybrid graphene/organic molecules and further investigation of exotic molecules in pursuit of multifunctional spintronic devices for advanced electronic applications.

4. Experimental Section/Methods

Device fabrication: The graphene flakes are exfoliated onto a doped silicon substrate with 300 nm of silicon oxide - Si/SiO₂ (300 nm), in a cleanroom environment using 3M scotch tape and the monolayer graphene is identified using an optical microscope under well-established optical contrast. Next, the lateral spin valve is fabricated following the standard nanofabrication protocols. The ferromagnetic TiO_x/Co electrodes are fabricated by electron-beam lithography, through first deposition of 3 Å of Ti and followed by 10 minutes of air-oxidation (to form the TiO_x) followed by subsequent depositions of 35 nm of Co and 45 nm of Au capping layer and lift-off in acetone. All layers are deposited in an ultra-high vacuum chamber with a base pressure of 10⁻⁸ mbar, using electron-beam evaporation for Ti and Co and thermal evaporation for Au. The width of the Co electrodes is either 300 nm or 150 nm to ensure different shape anisotropies and hence different coercive fields.

The transfer of the hBN mask slit onto the spin valve is completed through dry pick-up and drop technique. A Small piece of polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) gel-film is cut and placed onto a transparent slide glass and subsequently a convex drop of LCC polymer (nail varnish, colour crush Lakme) is deposited onto the PDMS. First, the pick-up of the hBN mask is done using the LCC polymer at a temperature $T = 60^{\circ}\text{C}$. Next, using a robotic mechanical arm the slide glass and hence the picked-up hBN mask is precisely aligned with respect to the spin valve, so the slit sits exactly in-between the two consecutive ferromagnetic electrodes of the device. Once aligned, the final drop of the hBN mask is completed at $T = 80^{\circ}\text{C}$. The transparency of the slide glass, PDMS and the LCC polymer allows to clearly track the pick-up, the alignment and the drop through an optical microscope. The obtained spin valve structure with the hBN mask on top is then dipped in a 1:3 mixture of acetone/isopropanol to dissolve the polymer, rinsed in isopropanol and blow dried using N₂ gun.

Finally, the device is introduced to an ultra-high vacuum evaporator chamber, with a base pressure of 10^{-11} mbar, to deposit the organic molecule. 5 nm of Fullerene C₆₀ molecular film (Sigma-Aldrich, purity \geq 99.5%) is deposited using high temperature Knudsen cell, at a rate of 0.1 \AA s^{-1} .

Electrical transport measurements: The device is wire bonded to a sample holder and installed in a physical property measurements system (PPMS) by Quantum design for transport measurements. The charge and spin transport measurements are carried out using a DC reversal technique with a Keithley 2182 nanovoltmeter and a Keithley 6221 current source. The back-gate voltage is applied to the highly doped Si substrate using a Keithley 2636B source meter.

Raman characterization: Micro-Raman measurements (Renishaw InVia Qontor micro-Raman instrument) were carried out at room temperature using as excitation source 532 nm laser, a diffraction grating of 1800 lines/mm and 100x objective.

Supporting Information

Enhanced spin relaxation time in a 2D/1D van der Waals hybrid heterostructure

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1. Raman spectroscopy characterization

The integrity of the C₆₀ film and the thickness of the graphene channel in the device is characterized by Raman spectroscopy (Renishaw InVia Qontor micro-Raman instrument) after the transport measurements. The zoomed-in spectrum of the characteristic graphene 2D peak is well fitted using a single Lorentzian function confirming on the monolayer graphene.

Figure S1. Detailed Raman spectrum of the 2D peak of graphene. The blue scattered symbols represent the experimental Raman spectrum while the solid black line is the fit of 2D peak using a single Lorentzian function.

2. Calculation of the resistance and the field effect mobility

The measured resistance of the hybrid graphene channel which is represented by the magenta plot of Figure 3b is the resistance of the channel that consists of both graphene/C₆₀ region with length $L_{Gr/C_{60}} = 0.5 \mu m$ and pristine graphene regions with length $L = L_T - L_{Gr/C_{60}} = 2.2 \mu m$. L_T is the total channel length between two consecutive electrodes.

Therefore, to extract the mobility of the graphene which is in direct contact with C₆₀ only (proximitized graphene/C₆₀), it is important to first find the resistance of this region. The resistance of this proximitized graphene/C₆₀ region is calculated using the following methodology. The total measured resistance of the hybrid graphene ($R_{Hybrid Gr}$) shown in Figure 3b of main text (magenta plot) is expressed as a sum of three resistances in series:

$$R_{Hybrid Gr} = R_1 + R_2 + R_3, \quad (1)$$

Where R_1 is the resistance of the first part of pristine graphene, R_2 is the resistance of the graphene/C₆₀ and R_3 is the resistance of the second pristine region of the hybrid channel, as shown in the schematic of the Figure S2 below.

Figure S2. The schematic of the device and the series resistor model used to calculate the resistance and the mobility of the proximitized graphene/C₆₀ region.

Next, taking into consideration that R_1 and R_3 are approximately the same as the measured resistance of the graphene in the pristine region R_{Gr} (the channel between F4 and F5) then

$$R_1 + R_3 \cong \frac{2.2}{2.7} R_{Gr} \quad (2)$$

Where 2.2 is the sum of the lengths of the first and second part of pristine graphene in the hybrid channel and 2.7 is the total length of the pristine channel as presented in the schematic of Figure S2. Replacing Equation (2) in (1) allows to find the resistance of the proximitized graphene/C₆₀ following:

$$R_2 = R_{Hybrid\ Gr} - \frac{2.2}{2.7} R_{Gr} \quad (3)$$

Following Equation (2), and with the experimentally measured resistances of the pristine graphene (R_{Gr}) and the hybrid graphene ($R_{Hybrid\ Gr}$) it is possible to have the resistance of the proximitized graphene/C₆₀ region.

Next, the field-effect mobility (μ_{FE}) of graphene in the pristine channel, in the hybrid channel, and of proximitized graphene/C₆₀ is extracted by first converting the resistances of those regions to conductivity (σ) following the equation:

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{R} \times \frac{L}{W} \quad (4)$$

Where L and W are the length and width of the graphene channel under study. Next, the carrier concentration (n) of the graphene is estimated from the surface charge density induced by the applied back-gate voltage (V_{bg}):

$$n = C_{bg} \times \frac{V_{bg} - V_{cnp}}{e} \quad (5)$$

Where C_{bg} is the back-gate capacitance, V_{bg} is the applied back-gate voltage, V_{CNP} is the voltage at the charge neutrality point of graphene and e is electronic charge. Consequently, the μ_{FE} is calculated from the V_{bg} dependence of the conductivity σ :

$$\mu_{FE} = \frac{d\sigma}{dV_{bg}} \times \frac{1}{C_{bg}} \quad (6)$$

Figure S3 shows the V_{bg} dependence of the μ_{FE} in the pristine graphene channel, the hybrid graphene channel and in the proximitized graphene/C₆₀ region.

Figure S3. Field-effect mobility of pristine graphene (black plot), of hybrid graphene (magenta plot) and of graphene/C₆₀ (olive plot) as a function of V_{bg} at $T = 100\text{K}$ in a) hole doping regime and b) electron doping regime.

3. Spin signal ΔR_{nl} as a function of carrier concentration

Figure S4 represents the calculated ΔR_{nl} of the spin valve measurement as a function of n . The ΔR_{nl} , over the entire range of n under study, is lower in the hybrid region than that of the pristine region.

Figure S4. Spin-valve measurements. a) R_{nl} measured for $n = 0.6 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, as function of B_y . The parallel and antiparallel states are labeled with blue arrows. b) ΔR_{nl} as a function of n . The black plots are for the pristine graphene, and the magenta plots are for the hybrid graphene. All measurements are recorded at $T = 100\text{K}$.

4. Reproducibility of the fabrication methodology

Figure S5 represents the summary of a second LSV device in which the organic compound is Cobalt phthalocyanine (CoPc). Figure S5a is a graphene LSV device with the hBN mask slit. F1 to F6 are the ferromagnetic Co electrodes. Figure S5b shows the transfer curve of the graphene channel in the pristine (between electrodes F4 and F5) and in the hybrid (between electrodes F5 and F6) regions. Figure S5c is the spin signal (ΔR_{nl}) as a function of n . The spin signal of the pristine graphene (black plot) is higher than the hybrid spin signal (orange plot), like the graphene/ C_{60} device. Figure S5d, 5e, and 5f represent the spin diffusion coefficient, spin lifetime and spin diffusion length of the pristine graphene (black plot) and hybrid graphene (orange plot) extracted from the fittings of the non-local Hanle

precession measurements. The effective spin transport properties of the graphene are enhanced in the hybrid region.

Figure S5. a) Optical image of the second LSV device. b) Transfer curve c) net spin signal (ΔR_{nl}). d) spin diffusion coefficient e) spin lifetime and f) spin diffusion length of pristine graphene (black plots) and hybrid graphene (orange plots) in the second device. All measurements are recorded at $T = 100\text{K}$.

5. Estimation of error on the simulated spin diffusion parameters

The fitting to extract D_s and τ_s is done by running a simulation at different values of magnetic field between 0 T and 0.3 T. The Hanle precession curve data is symmetric so only one sign of the field needs to be considered. The root mean square differences (RMSE) between the simulated points and the experimental data is recorded. This process is repeated for a large range of D_s and τ_s values. The values given in Figure S6 represent the combination of D_s and τ_s which minimize the RMSE. The uncertainty is calculated as the distance in the parameter (D_s, τ_s) space over which the RMSE does not

change significantly from the minimum. Consequently, the estimated error value for τ_s would be ± 50 ps and for D_s ± 0.02 $m^2 s^{-1}$.

Figure S6. The array of D_s and τ_s values with the calculated uncertainty. The diagram is for one simulated gate voltage $V_g = 10$ V.

6. SEM images of the final LSV device

Figure S7 displays the SEM images of the final LSV device. The SEM image of the left panel shows the ferromagnetic TiO_x/Co injectors and detectors (orange), the hBN stencil mask (green) and the monolayer graphene (blue). The right panel is the magnified SEM image, where the slit of the hBN stencil mask is clearly observed.

Figure S7. Low and high magnification SEM images of the final LSV device. The ferromagnetic electrodes are shown in orange, the hBN stencil mask in green and the monolayer graphene in blue.

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